

Chunqiu fanlu

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Entry tags: Confucian (rujia 儒家) Traditions, Religious Group, Chinese Religion, Imperial Confucian Traditions, Early Chinese text, Text

The text *Chunqiu fanlu* is a compendium of Chinese ethical and political thought traditionally ascribed to a pivotal scholar from the Former Han dynasty (206 BCE – 9 CE), Dong Zhongshu (c. 195 to 115 BCE.). Dong Zhongshu was a leading exegete of the *Gongyang Zhuan* (*Gongyang Commentary on the Spring and Autumn Annals*), an early Han commentary of the *Spring and Autumn Annals* (*Chunqiu*). The Chinese tradition credits him with an important role in the formation of “Han Confucianism” as the state ideology during the reign of Emperor Wu (140 – 134 BCE). But, this view is radically challenged by contemporary scholarship. This lengthy, rich and comprehensive work consisting of 82 chapters (*pian*), of which 79 have survived, has been commented upon in China throughout history as one of the most authoritative texts of Chinese ruism (Confucianism.) However, in terms of its authorship, dating and even in its textual preservation, the CQFL is a rather problematic text. While there is no certain answer on the question on what parts of the CQFL can be authentically traced to Dong Zhongshu, some chapters certainly originate from different sources. Most of the recent scholars agree that the CQFL is a collection of heterogeneous material from early Han and even post-Han scholarly work assembled by an anonymous compiler. The text contains a great diversity of subject matter. Sarah Queen and John Major persuasively argued that the text is arranged according to the principles that guided its anonymous compiler. They singled out five units. The first unit, “Exegetical Principles”, consisting of the first seventeen chapters represents the earliest and most probably authentic part of the whole compilation. These chapters interpret the principles of the *Spring and Autumn Annals* based on the *Gongyang* commentary. The “Monarchical Principles” (chapters 18-22) focus on the techniques for maintaining the power and authority of the ruler. They establish a kind of naturalistic approach which seeks normativity in the realm of nature. The third group, “Regulatory Principles” (chapters 23 to 28) addresses the regulations the ruler should observe after receiving the Mandate of Heaven. The “Ethical Principles” (chapters 29 to 42) group discusses the fundamental virtues and ideas esteemed by ruist scholars, such as humaneness *ren* 仁, righteousness *yi* 義, wisdom *zhi* 智, virtue *de* 德, the rectification of names *zheng ming* 正名, and filial piety *xiao* 孝. The “Yin-Yang Principles” group focuses on the cosmology of yin-yang and the four seasons in relation to the ruler’s emotions, actions, and policies. “Five-Phase Principles” chapters develop the art of rulership based on Five Phase *wu xing* cosmology. “Ritual Principles” group, constituted of twelve thematically linked chapters, describes various aspects of ritual obligations and sacrifice from the perspective of the *Gongyang* commentary on the *Spring and Autumn*. The “Heavenly Principles” (chapters 77 to 82) contain some rather corrupted chapters grouped around the idea of Heaven as the source of political and moral principles. They correlate the way of Heaven with the physical cultivation and governing the country. Please note that all translations are taken from the ebook version of Sarah Queen and John Major’s “*Luxuriant Gems of the Spring and Autumn*), Columbia University Press: 2015. <https://www.amazon.co.uk/Luxuriant-Spring-Autumn-Translations-Classics-ebook/dp/B017QL99WU>

Date Range: 2 BCE - 7 CE

Region: China: the Han Dynasty

Region tags: China

The Han Dynasty as its greatest extent.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Loewe, Michael. *Dong Zhongshu, a “Confucian” Heritage and the Chunqiu fanlu*. Leiden: Brill. 2011.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

– Source 1: Loewe, Michael. *Divination, mythology and monarchy in Han China*. Cambridge: University Press. 1994.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

– Source 1: Gassmann, Robert H. *Tung Chung-shu Ch'un-ch'iu Fan-lu. Üppiger Tau des Frühling- und Herbst-Klassikers: Übersetzung und Annotation der Kapitel eins bis sechs*. Bern: Peter Lang. 1988.

– Source 1: *Chunqiu fanlu huijiao jishi* 春秋繁露彙校集釋, by Dong Zhongshu, with commentary by Zhong Zhaopeng 鍾肇鵬; Zhou Guidian 周桂鈿, Li Xi 李曦, Yu Shoukui 于首奎. Shijiazhuang: Hebei renmin chubanshe, 2005.

– Source 1: Queen, Sarah A., John S. Major (eds. and trans.). *Luxuriant Gems of the Spring and Autumn*, attributed to Dong Zhongshu. New York: Columbia University Press. 2015.

– Source 1: Arbuckle, Gary. “Restoring Dong Zhongshu (BCE 195-115): An Experiment in Historical and Philosophical Reconstruction.” Ph.D. diss., University of British Columbia. 1991.

– Source 2: Cheng, Anne. *Étude sur le confucianisme han: l'élaboration d'une tradition exégétique sur les classiques*. Paris: Collège de France et Institut des Hautes Études Chinoises. 1985.

– Source 1: *Chunqiu fanlu yizheng* 春秋繁露義證 (Verification of the Meanings in the Luxuriant Dew of the Spring and Autumn) with commentary by Su Yu 蘇輿. Beijing: Zhonghua Shuju. 1992.

– Source 1: Gentz, Joachim. *Language of Heaven, Exegetical Skepticism and the Reinsertion of Religious Concepts in the Gongyang Tradition*. In Lagerwey, John, Kalinowski, Marc (eds.). *Early Chinese Religion: Part One: Shang through Han (1250 BC – 220 AD)*, Vol. 2. Leiden: Brill. 2009

– Source 3: Gentz, Joachim. *Das Gongyang zhuan: Auslegung und Kanonisierung der Frühlings- und Herbstannalen (Chunqiu)*. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz. 2001.

– Source 1: John Lagerwey, Marc Kalinowski. *Early Chinese Religion, Part One: Shang through Han (1250 BC- 220 AD)* (2 vols.). Leiden: Brill. 2008.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://ctext.org/chun-qiu-fan-lu>

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: <https://ctext.org/chun-qiu-fan-lu>

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

Specify type of paper

– Specify: Woodblocks and movable type prints.

Notes: The book under the title "Chunqiu fanlu" existed in Sui and Tang times as it was cited by several writers. During this period the woodblock technique was in use. Woodblocks were the printing method for several different versions of the text which existed in Song times. There is a copy of the text from 1516 (format 14X13) in movable type print, which was not widely used in China.

Reference: Loewe, Michael. *Dong Zhongshu, a 'confucian' Heritage and the Chunqiu Fanlu*. BRILL, 2011.

https://books.google.com/books/about/Dong_Zhongshu_a_Confucian_Heritage_and_t.html?hl=&id=yeN5DwAAQBAJ.

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: The field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

↳ Tomb

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

↳ Cemetery

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

↳ Temple

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

↳ Shrine

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

↳ Altar

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

↳ Devotional marker

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

↳ Cenotaph

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

↳ Church

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

↳ Mosque

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

↳ Synagogue

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

↳ Triumphal Arch

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

↳ Monument

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

↳ Mass Gathering Point

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

↳ Cave(s)

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

↳ Hilltops

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

↳ Domestic contexts

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

↳ Library/archive

– Yes

Notes: Some editions of the Chunqiu fanlu are held in mainland China and Taipei (National Central Library). Some copies are held in the Library of Congress, Washington.

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

↳ Specify

– Specify: No.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Chunqiu fanlu is a rather problematic text in terms of its origin and composition. It is a collection of heterogeneous writings which may be ascribed to different sources. It is not known the origin of these writings and hence the field does not know whether the production of some of its chapters was funded by the polity.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Notes: The text is not a sacred religious text as it is not written in a sacred language, its compilation is not dictated by One etc. Nevertheless, the content of some chapters does discuss some religious and natural phenomenon in a certain way which may be associated with the sacred. For instance, some of the chapters discuss the performance of certain rituals (such as invocation and stopping of rain); some of the chapters discuss the state cults to heaven and earth; some of them explore natural phenomena as warnings to future leaders etc.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

Intended Audience

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Several chapters of the text describe how to perform some rituals, but it is not known whether they were employed in ritual practice or whether and in which way their description of these rituals affected the ritual practice. For instance, some chapters describe the performance of the rituals for seeking and preventing rain. The rituals for controlling rain were among the most enduring rituals in Chinese tradition. One may ask whether the Chunqiu fanlu as one of the most important premodern Chinese texts had an impact on them.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: The title "Chunqiu fanlu" was affixed to the text somewhere between third and sixth centuries.

From the period of the third to the eleventh century, the Chunqiu, was mentioned and available in different forms and lengths. Until 11th century there were different copies of the book in circulation.

Reference: Loewe, Michael. Dong Zhongshu, a 'confucian' Heritage and the Chunqiu Fanlu. BRILL, 2011. https://books.google.com/books/about/Dong_Zhongshu_a_Confucian_Heritage_and_t.html?hl=&id=yeN5DwAAQBAJ.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

↳ Content of text?

– No

Notes: Among the different editions of the text one may find differences in arrangement of some chapters and textual differences which are the results of copying and different interpretations.

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Notes: Some parts of the Chunqiu fanlu represent the explanations and ideas of the Gongyang school, later known as "New Text Confucianism." In particular, this refers to the first seventeen chapters of the text which illuminate the principles of the Spring and Autumn. In this context, some parts of the text may be seen as part of the Gongyang tradition which intended to study, disseminate and comment on the Spring and Autumn.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: No.

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Ritual list

Notes: The Chunqiu fanlu describes and regulates various rituals performed for different purposes.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Yes

Notes: Taking that some of the chapters of the Chunqiu fanlu are written by Dong Zhongshu and his disciples, the lineage established by the text may be seen in this master-disciples relation.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

↳ Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?

– I don't know

↳ Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?
– Field doesn't know

↳ How is the lineage established?
– Student-Teacher Relationship

Does the text express a formal legal code?
– I don't know

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?
– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?
– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?
– Yes

Notes: Several chapters of the Chunqiu fanlu do reflect a belief in the afterlife according to which ancestors reside in Heaven. According to Chapter 23, "The Three Dynasties' Alternating Regulations of Simplicity and Refinement" the sagely nature and Heavenly mandate could take form in the ancestors. Following this view, these chapters advocate performing sacrifices to the ancestors, on part of the ruler and his people. For instance, Chapter 6, "The Kingly Way", which interprets the chronicle Spring and Autumn, while referring to the golden age of China when the Five Emperors and Three Kings governed, states that people "performed the ancestral sacrifices to the former emperors so that their ancestors accompanied Heaven. " Performing sacrifices they "gown before the ruler's more remote ancestors in the ancestral temple." The same chapter holds the view that the ruler ought to cause his people to make offerings to the ancestors at the temples. Chapter 65, "Sayings Pertaining to the Suburban Sacrifice" also proposes sacrifices to ancestors.

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?
– Yes

Notes: Afterlife is located in Heaven.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

– Yes

Notes: Hun remained in the body of the deceased, i.e. in graves.

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

Are formal burials present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: In the part of the text which elucidates the principles of the Spring and Autumn, several times are discussed the reasons behind the Spring and Autumn's record of the burials of prominent persons.

↳ As cenotaphs?

– No

↳ In cemetery?

– No

↳ Family tomb-crypt?

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities)?

– No

↳ Other formal burial type?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s)?

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deified human?

– No

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero?

– No

↳ For the veneration of a deceased person(s)?

– Yes

↳ For the veneration of a deified human?

– No

↳ For the veneration of a deceased hero?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Notes: Heaven (Tian).

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

Notes: The supreme high god is Heaven, which is the most honoured of all the spirits that populate the numinous realm. Heaven is an object of worship of the emperor. Heaven is the great lord of the spirits (Chapter 65, "Sayings Pertaining to the Suburban Sacrifice.")

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

Notes: Chapter 18, "Departing from and Conforming to Fundamentals", states that Heaven extensively loves all creatures. It bestows its gifts below by which it is humane (ren). Chapter 30, "The Necessity of (Being) Humane and Wise" states that even when Heaven sends natural disasters and bizarre events it is not because it wants to harm others, but because it wants to make the ruling family change its way of ruling, and

rescue it from doing wrong. According to Chapter 19, "Establishing the Originating Spirit", Heaven engenders people with filial piety and fraternal love.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– I don't know

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– I don't know

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

Notes: Heaven may recognise one's sincerity.

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– I don't know

↳ Has other knowledge of this world

– I don't know

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Notes: Chapter 77, "Conform to Heaven's Way", states that Heaven "expresses its will by means of living things." Chapter 2, "Jade Cup", and Chapter 9, "Waxing and Waning in Accord with the Root", state that human beings receive their destinies through Heaven. Similarly, Chapter 70, "Following Orders" states that humans receive their fate through Heaven. A ruler receives the Mandate of Heaven (to found a new dynasty).

↳ Can reward

– Yes

Notes: Chapter 71, "An Official Response Regarding the Suburban Sacrifice", quotes the Odes saying that brightly watchful and reverent King Wen served the High God, and so secured many blessings. Chapter 6, "The Kingly Way", states that Heaven rewards people which cultivate virtue: "People cultivated virtue and found beauty in the good. With hair unbound and eating whatever came to hand, they wandered freely. They did not covet wealth or nobility. They were ashamed of doing wrong and did not transgress. Fathers did not [have to] mourn their sons; older brothers did not [have to] mourn their younger brothers. Poisonous insects did not sting; wild animals did not strike; fierce beasts did not butt. Thus Heaven sent down sweet dew on their behalf. Vermilion grasses came to life; sweet springs issued forth; winds and rains were timely; excellent millet flourished."

↳ Can punish

– Yes

Notes: If the ruler fails to perform a ritual to Heaven or errs in performing the ritual, he can expect disasters, such as drought, famine, starvation, death etc. Disasters correspond to the degree to which he transgressed the ritual. The source of a state's survival or destruction, blessings or disasters, can be traced to the conduct of its ruler and the extent to which he follows active or passive policies in accordance with Heaven

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Notes: Chapter 70, "Following Orders", states that with respect to Heaven, humans receive their fate in accordance with Heaven.

↳ Exhibits positive emotion

– Yes

Notes: Heaven impartially loves all the people.

↳ Exhibits negative emotion

– No

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– No

↳ Can be hurt?

– No

↳ Can be tricked?

– No

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– Yes

Notes: The emperor should perform sacrifice to all the spirits of the realm, including lesser gods than Heaven, but if he fails to offer a sacrifice to Heaven, service to these lesser spirits will not make the realm prosperous. The emperor should perform sacrifice to Heaven, while regional lord should perform sacrifice to the God of the soil.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature

– Specify: Harmony, severity. Also, Heaven's Way is constant, singular (not dualistic); so the things that are mutually opposed are not permitted to arise simultaneously.

Notes: According to Chapter 18, hiding its form is the means by which Heaven is divine (shen). Showing forth its light is the means by which it is illuminated (ming).

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

Notes: Heaven's command is called mandate. Chapter 30, "The Necessity of (Being) Humane and Wise" states that Heaven may warn, inform and threaten a ruler. Heaven sends down warnings in a form of natural disasters and threats manifested as bizarre events. This is the way how Heaven communicates with the ruler. If the ruler does not accept these warnings and modify his ruling, Heaven will frighten him with bizarre events. The text also states that people receive Heaven's commands, and if they disobey them the result is in cutting off Heaven's endowed relationships.

↳ In waking, everyday life

– No

↳ In dreams

– No

↳ In trance possession

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists

– Yes

Notes: Heaven communicates through religious specialists, but also the text states that a noble man may understand Heaven's command.

↳ Only through monarch

– Yes

↳ Other form of communication with living

– Yes

Notes: Chapter 35, "Deeply Examine Names and Designations", states that although Heaven does not speak, it causes people to communicate its intentions; although it does not act it causes people to realize its centrality. Heaven's intentions are placed in the ruler (one who received the Mandate of Heaven.) Chapter 30 states that people inside their hearts may find what Heaven desires, and also observing affairs one may realise Heaven's will.

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– Yes

Notes: The text stresses the mutual interaction between Heaven and humankind. The form of communication with Heaven is to offer sacrifice to Heaven, obey its command, serve Heaven by following the path of filial piety, show fondness for the correct and upright etc. If the people follow this way, spirits will hear them and give them great blessings.

↳ Can the audience communicate directly to gods through the text?

– No

↳ Can the audience communicate through supernatural intermediaries to the high-god, as a result of the text?

– I don't know

↳ Are there notions of inspiration or inspired knowledge?

– No

↳ Are there rituals required to attain inspired knowledge?

– I don't know

↳ What concepts of inspiration exist? (e.g. clairvoyance, insights, vision of the divine world, awareness of divine omnipresent agency or omnipotence, sight or vision beyond the five senses).

– I don't know

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

Notes: The text mentions ancestral spirits.

↳ Human spirits can be seen

– No

Notes: The spirits cannot be seen nor heard. But, one who makes a proper sacrifice "can reach what cannot be seen or heard", states Chapter 76. If one makes a sacrifice with sincere intentions, respect and purity then the ancestral spirits arrive to accept offerings.

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt

– No

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Notes: Human spirits may affect human affairs, thus the text examines how human can receive the efficacy of the ghosts and spirits.

↳ Human spirits can reward

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can punish

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have memory of life

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living

– No

Notes: In early China ancestral spirits are described as responsive to human actions and the purpose of sacrifice was to connect with the spirits.

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: The text mentions the spirits of the grain and soil, of the mountains and rivers.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– No

Notes: The spirits cannot be seen neither heard. But, one who makes a proper sacrifice "can see what cannot be seen", states Chapter 76.

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region
– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
– I don't know

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
– I don't know

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
– I don't know

Notes: According to Chapter 76, the ancestral spirits know if one sacrifice with the sincere intentions, only then the spirits will accept one's offerings. Chapter 76 states that the ancestral spirits accept one's offerings only if sacrifice is carried with innermost sincere intentions.

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)
– No

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
– I don't know

↳ Have other knowledge of this world
– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
– Yes

Notes: The text raises the question how humans can receive the assistance of ghosts and spirits.

↳ Supernatural beings can reward
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can punish
– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– No

Notes: The supernatural beings react on proper or improper sacrifices to them. This is the only communication with the living according to the text

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– Yes

Notes: The sacrificial offerings (food) id offered to ghosts and spirits which imply that they ossess hunger.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

– Specify: No.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

Notes: The text mention the supreme deity and lesser spirits.

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– I don't know

↳ Other organization of pantheon?

– Specify: No.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: No

Does the text guide divination practices?

– Yes

↳ Divination by examination of the extra (animal remains)

– No

↳ Divination through human communication?

– No

↳ Divination through animal-behavior?

– No

↳ Divination through non-living material?

– Other [specify]: No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Heaven acts as a judge of human affairs, it has a knowledge of human affairs which implies the fact that it also monitors people. However, the text does not explicitly state this.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text states that Heaven's Mandate brings calamity to the evil. The source of a state's destruction or disasters can be traced to the conduct of its ruler and the extent to which he follows active or passive policies in accordance with Heaven.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– Yes

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– Yes

↳ Done randomly

– I don't know

↳ Other

– Yes

Notes: If a ruler does not serve, emulate Heaven and obey Heaven's will, he will lose the mandate of Heaven and he will receive a sort of punishment.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The text does not discuss this topic.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– Yes

Notes: A state's destruction and disasters can be traced to the conduct of its ruler and the extent to which he follows policies in accordance with Heaven.

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Consists of bad luck?

– I don't know

↳ Political failure?

– Yes

↳ Defeat in battle?

– Yes

↳ Crop failure or bad weather?

– Yes

↳ Disaster on journeys?

– I don't know

↳ Mild sensory displeasure?

– I don't know

↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?

– I don't know

↳ Sickness or illness?

– Yes

↳ Impaired reproduction?

– Yes

↳ Back luck visited on descendants?

– I don't know

↳ Other?

– Specify: No.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings reward after receiving proper sacrifice. Heaven protects the good and rewards only those who are virtuous. If the ruler follows policies in accordance with Heaven, his state will survive and receive blessings. Chapter 67 states: "This King Wen, watchful and reverent, brightly served the High God and so secured many blessings." "Many blessings" does not refer to his person but to his meritorious service [to Heaven]. It refers to what Heaven blesses."

↳ Done only by high god

– No

Notes: High god, but also the spirits of mountains and rivers influence the human world and can reward.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence

– Yes

Notes: Proper sacrifice is made in order to avoid the punishment of Heaven, and to receive a reward, so consequently, exemplary sacrifice is encouraged.

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– I don't know

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– I don't know

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– I don't know

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized?

– Yes

Notes: The text emphasizes that ruler which serves and emulates Heaven and obeys Heaven's will receive success.

↳ Consists of good luck?

– Yes

↳ Consists of political success or power?

– Yes

↳ Consists of success in battle?

– Yes

Notes: Chapter 1, "King Zhuang of Chu" states: " An Ode declares: 'King Wen received the Mandate of Heaven; he achieved his martial success.'"

↳ Consists of peace or social stability?

– Yes

↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?

– Yes

↳ Consists of success on journeys?

– I don't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– No

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?
 - I don't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?
 - I don't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?
 - I don't know
- ↳ Other?
 - Specify: No.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction?

– Present (but not emphasized)

Notes: Chapter 4 "Jade Brilliance" asserts that those who make good deeds which do not comply with the standard cannot be emulated. If one rejects these deeds, then one rejects their good intentions. If one emulates them, then one will harm the standards set down by the king. This is the reason why these b deeds are not recorded by the Spring and Autumn Annals. Nevertheless, the Spring and Autumn stress the good intentions. If an individual sets his/her will on humaneness, she will be free from wrong.

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts

– No

↳ Moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities

– No

↳ Linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma)

– Yes

Notes: In some chapters they are linked to Heaven and Earth conceived as cosmic entities. The ruler should follow Heaven, while his ministers should follow Earth.

↳ Linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being

– Yes

Notes: Heaven is conceived as an anthropomorphic being. The sages emulate Heaven in creating the Way

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being

– Yes

Notes: Several chapters of the text mention the command of Heaven. Chapter 70 "Following Orders" states that those who disregard Heaven's command will be punished (cutting off from their Heaven-endowed relationship.) Chapter 44 "The Kingly Way Penetrates Three" asserts that the ruler emulates Heaven's commands and circulates them among the people.

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no (sic: have no?) special connection to the metaphysical

– Yes

Notes: Some chapters derive moral norms from nature (in particular, chapter 18 to 22.)

↳ Moral norms apply to (select all that apply)

– All individuals within society

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

Notes: The text does not pay much attention to the virtue of courage in battle. In general, as Chapter 14, "Images for the Regulation of Dress" states, resorting to warfare as a way to stop the enemy was not prized. From this may be derived a focus on different virtues, such as civility etc, and not courage. One of the rare places which mention courage occurs in chapter 28. It describes ancient worthy regional overlords as being "brave as tigers."

↳ Courage (generic)

– Yes

Notes: In some of the chapters, courage is considered to be an attribute of a worthy man. Chapter 65 describes worthy people as being noble, brave and eminent. In Chapter 28 one of the four categories in which officials were categorised is "brave officials" (the others are talented, eminent, and prominent.) One man in ten is designated as "brave."

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– I don't know

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

Notes: Selflessness appears as a virtue of officials. (Kao gong ming chapter)

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– Yes

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

↳ Cooperation

– Yes

Notes: In particular, the text stresses cooperation among superiors and inferiors.

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– No

↳ Moderation/frugality

– Yes

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– I don't know

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– No

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

↳ Power/status/nobility

– Yes

↳ Humility/modesty

– Yes

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– Yes

↳ Optimism/hope

– No

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– Yes

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– Yes

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– Yes

Notes: Offering sacrifices to ancestors and parents require being bathed, being pure and clean.

↳ Other important virtues

– Yes

Notes: Ritual propriety, civility, clarity, brotherly love, magnanimity.

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

Notes: Chapter 77 "Conform to Heaven's Way" recommends partial sexual abstinence as the technique of nourishing life (yang sheng), promoting health, longevity and immortality. Regarding sexual intercourse, it advocates timeliness, i.e. to act following the norms of Heaven and to be in accord with the movement of yin and yang. It holds a view that untimeliness in seeking pleasure harms one's qi (cherishing the Heavenly qi is the most important aspect of nourishing life) what leads to illness and death. For instance, the chapter recommends "sparing in spring and abstinence in summer"; not having intercourse "when the (yin) qi has not yet reached the limit of its flourishing." The chapter also mentions how often to seek sexual pleasure when in puberty, in the middle ages, in old age, etc. In Chapter 74, "Seeking Rain" sexual activity (among the wives and husbands between the officials and commoners) is required during drought in order to facilitate intercourse of yin and yang as part of the ritual of seeking rain.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

↳ Monogamy (males)

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (females)

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (females)

– Yes

Notes: The text prohibits marrying one's own close relative.

Does the text require castration?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Notes: The chapters which describe rituals for invoking and stopping rain mention fasting. Praying and fasting for three days were part of the performance of the ritual. Five men and five widowers were fasting for three days and danced around the dragons. Chapter 68, "The Four Seasonal Sacrificial Rites" discusses fasting (also being bathed, pure, clean and reverent) as a precondition for offering sacrifices to ancestors and parents.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– Yes

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

What is the average interval of time between performances?

– I don't know

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– Field doesn't know

Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– Field doesn't know

Are there orthodoxy checks?

– I don't know

Are there orthopraxy checks?

– I don't know

Does participation entail synchronic practices?

– Yes

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– I don't know

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– Yes

Notes: An emperor is called the Son of Heaven.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology is universal?

– No

Notes: Son of Heaven is a title reserved only for an emperor.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology is widespread?

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon?

– I don't know

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– Yes

Notes: Music and dancing.

↳ Drama?

– No

↳ Comedy?

– No

↳ Tragedy?

– No

↳ Epic entertainment?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

Notes: The text stresses timely sacrifice dictating when the sacrificial offerings have to be presented. Chapter 66, quoting the Spring and Autumn, states that the king's sacrifices at the ancestral temple

should follow the changes in the four seasons and the offerings at the suburban altar follow the beginning of the new year.

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– Yes

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– Yes

↳ Are they mandatory?

– Yes

↳ Are they composed of valuable objects?

– Yes

Notes: Chapter 69 , "The Suburban Sacrifice" mentions using jade objects in sacrificing spirits.

↳ Are they composed of daily-life objects?

– Yes

Notes: The rituals for seeking or stopping rain require the preparation of food (grain, salt, wine, meat) for the altar of the soil.

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches)?

– I don't know

↳ Are there particular smells associated with material offerings?

– No

↳ Are there particular visual stimuli (colors, symbols) associated with the offerings? (I.e. 'must be bright' 'must include red')

– Yes

Notes: Chapter 23, "The Three Dynasties' Alternating Regulations of Simplicity and

Refinement" discusses the ritual regulations that a dynastic founder should follow. It determines the Three Sequences he should establish. These sequences are symbolised by the black, red and white colour. In addition to colours, the shapes of these animals are determined. During the Black Sequence, the ritual colour is black. This means that the clothes worn at court should be in black, pendants of official caps are black, imperial chariots and horses are black, a sacrificial animal is black, imperial flags and precious jades are black, musical instruments are black etc. After the black, there is a red and white sequence.

↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?

– Yes

↳ By the community?

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text follows the standards of the Spring and Autumn according which emperor once a year presents sacrificial offerings to Heaven at the suburban altar and four times at the ancestral temple.

↳ Is it required?

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance)?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other?

–Specify: No.

– Yes

Notes: The offerings at the ancestral temple follow the changes in the four seasons.

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– Yes

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– Yes

↳ Are they mandatory?

– Yes

↳ Are they composed of valuable objects?

– Yes

↳ Are they composed of daily-life objects?

– Yes

Notes: Various chapters mention different sacrificial offerings dependent on the purpose of sacrifice, including scallion and wheat, pigs, live fish, dark wine, grain, and salt.

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches)?

– I don't know

↳ Are there particular smells associated with material offerings?

– No

↳ Are there particular visual stimuli (colors, symbols) associated with the offerings? (I.e. 'must be bright' 'must include red')

– I don't know

↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?

– Yes

↳ By the community?

– Yes

Notes: Chapter 74 "Seeking Rain" requires the people praying at the altars and the members of households to sacrifice to the door in order to seek rain.

↳ By specific individuals?

– Yes

Notes: The emperor must follow the proper sequence of sacrifice in performing sacrifices to Heaven.

↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Is it required?

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance)?

– I don't know

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions?

– Yes

Notes: Chapter 74 "Seeking Rain" states that on the eighth day of the seeking rain ritual, the ruler should construct an earthen altar measuring eight feet square outside the eastern gate of the city, with openings on all four sides. In addition, it requires excavating a tunnel through the altar of the soil to connect it with the watercourse beyond the city gate. Also, a pool eight feet square and one foot deep should be made, felt with water. Five frogs should be put into it.

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff?

– I don't know

↳ Other?

–Specify: No.

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– An empire

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 206 BCE - 6 CE

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: No.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Notes: The text do stress that the role of the government is firstly to provide food and drink to people and then to educate them, but do not specify the methods to achieve that.

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– I don't know

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– Yes

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– Yes

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– Yes

Notes: The chapters differ in their viewpoints regarding how the ruler should manage a bureaucracy.

Does the text regulate bureaucracy permanently?

– Yes

Does the text regulate bureaucracy temporarily/seasonally?

– Yes

Does the text dictate how the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group?

– Yes

↳ Does the text dictate how individuals interact with other institutional bureaucracies?
– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate the primary supporting income of the place?
– I don't know

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out land?
– I don't know

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out tools?
– I don't know

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?
– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?
– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?
– Yes

Notes: The rulers who resort to warfare, who rely on force rather than virtue, are harshly criticised. During warfare people suffer, and warfare kills them, so warfare does not love people. Warfare as the method of stopping warfare is not the sagely way.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?
– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Notes: The preparation of food is shortly mentioned in Chapter 75, "Stopping Rain" which describes a ritual for stopping rain. As part of this ritual, invokers should prepare a young pig, grain, salt and wine for the altar of the god of soil.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2 BCE - 6 CE

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